

IN-SITU MIXING AND PRINTING OF CONTINUOUS CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOSET COMPOSITES

J. HARES | P. A. KELLY | M. A. BATTLE | BICKERTON
CACM, THE UNIVERSITY OF AUCKLAND

Centre for
Advanced
Composite
Materials

CONTENT

- Motivation and Background
- Material Characterisation
- Process Characterisation
- Printer Prototype

Centre for
Advanced
Composite
Materials

Why Composite Printing?

Automation!

Composites are hard to make

Better parts!

Has anyone else done this?

Of course they have!

But there is a long way to go...

- Low material properties.
- Low volume fraction/no compaction.
- Thermoset printing is underdeveloped.

What will we do?

Gaps in the state of the art

- Thermoset printing is not in commercial use.
- *Very little* investigation into processing behaviour.
- Thermoset printing is underdeveloped.

Scope

'Processing-science based design'

- Resin characterisation.
- Fibre characterisation.
- Build a prototype

Resin Characterisation

SOLID EPOXY-BASED PRINTING PROCESS CONCEPT

Resin Characterisation EXPERIMENTS

DSC

DMA

Rheology

Filament Count

Filament Width

Tow Characteristics and Infiltration EXPERIMENTS

Tow/Metal Friction

Radial Compaction

In-Line Infiltration

Tow Characteristics and Infiltration

FRICITION MEASUREMENT SETUP

Centre for
Advanced
Composite
Materials

- Need to measure coefficient of friction between iris and fibre material.
- Pull tensioned fibre over drum made from iris material.
 - 4340 steel, 2-4Ra isotropic roughness.
- Capstan Equation used to calculate coefficient of friction.

$$\mu_{app} = \ln \left(\frac{T_2}{T_1} \right) \frac{1}{\theta}$$

- μ_{app} - Applied friction coefficient.
- $T_{1,2}$ - Fibre tension on each side of drum.
- θ - Wrap angle.

Tow Characteristics and Infiltration

RADIAL COMPACTION, IRIS MECHANISM SETUP

- Need to measure σ_c and V_f relationship for single fibre tows.
 - Must be able to vary opening area.
- Ability to characterise more complex behaviour.
- *Solution: 'Iris' mechanism experiment.*

Laser
distance
sensor

Iris opening

Linear actuator

Printer Design

ZONE #1 – RESIN STORAGE, PUMPING, & MIXING

Centre for
Advanced
Composite
Materials

THE UNIVERSITY OF
AUCKLAND
Te Whare Wānanga o Tāmaki Makaurau
NEW ZEALAND

Printer Design

ZONE #2 - DRIVE

Printer Design

ZONE #3 - NOZZLE

Centre for
Advanced
Composite
Materials

THE UNIVERSITY OF
AUCKLAND
Te Whare Wānanga o Tāmaki Makaurau
NEW ZEALAND

Printer Prototype

CURRENT STATUS

Centre for
Advanced
Composite
Materials

THE UNIVERSITY OF
AUCKLAND
Te Whare Wānanga o Tāmaki Makaurau
NEW ZEALAND

Printer Prototype

CURRENT STATUS

Maximum Processing Temperature

Temperature/Viscosity

Pump Flow Rate @105°C

Remaining steps:

1. Flow rate consistency.
2. Resin and fibre together.
3. Microscopy of composite.
4. Tensile test of composite.

A novel concept for a continuous fibre 3D print head has been developed, which infiltrates a carbon fibre tow with a thermoset epoxy in-situ.

The print head has been designed from a series of in-depth material and process characterisation experiments, including:

- DSC and Rheometric studies on an epoxy, solid at room temperature.
- Fibre tow frictions, and radial compaction studies.
- Extension and testing of the Siphon tow infiltration technique developed by the Leibniz-Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe, to small scale.

The prototype print head is currently being commissioned and debugging. The latest progress will be presented at ICCM23.

Acknowledgements

The first author acknowledges funding provided by the University of Auckland, through a UoA Doctoral Scholarship.